

Chavin Culture Religion

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Entry tags: Pre-Inka Religions, Andes, Peru, Religious Group, Language, Unknown

Chavin de Huantar is a ceremonial center from the Formative Period in the central Andes. Chronologically in the middle Formative (1300 BCE, in the earliest structure) to the Late Formative 850BCE-500BCE (Rick et al. 2009; Contreras, 2024). It is the center of 3 spheres of interaction: coastal, mountain and northern. The most representative is its stone art, the most representative structures being the "galleries" and the lithic art.

Date Range: 1300 BCE - 500 BCE

Region: Sites related to Chavin during the Late Formative

Region tags: Peru

Territory with Formative sites that share elements with Chavin. To the north, there are Cerro Blanco and Huaca Partida in Nepeña, Ancash (Tello, 2019; Ikehara and Shibata, 2008), while to the south it would reach Carhua in Paracas, Ica. To the southwest, Campanayuc rumi (Wilcas, Ayacucho; Matsumoto and Caverro, 2012). Although there are discussions about what is or is not "properly" Chavin in other regions such as Jequetepeque (Lambayeque), some authors when talking about the late Formative refer to 3 spheres of interaction and although Chavin is not part of any of them, it is located in the middle of them (Kaulicke et al., 2019).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: Lumberas, C. (2014). Excavaciones en la Plaza Circular y el Atrio del Lanzón en Chavin de Huántar. Instituto andino de Estudios Arqueológico - Sociales
- Fuente 2: Tello, J. (2019 [1960]). Chavin. Cultura matriz de la civilización Andina.
- Fuente 3: Burger, R. (1998). Excavaciones en Chavin de Huántar. Fondo editorial PUCP

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- URL de la Fuente 1: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/33693327_Architectural_Sequence_and_Chronology_at_Chavin_de_Huantar_Peru_PhD_Dissertation_Dep
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Kembel, S. (2001). Architectural Sequence and Chronology at Chavin de Huántar, Perú. [Ph.D Dissertation]. Department of Anthropological Sciences, Stanford University.
- URL de la Fuente 2: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S104061822400140X>
- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Contreras, D. (2024). Archaeological 14C assemblages and the Chavin Phenomenon in the Central Andes. Quaternary International,
- URL de la Fuente 3: https://www.academia.edu/53146807/NUEVOS_CONCEPTOS_SOBRE_LA_SECUENCIA_CONSTRUCTIVA_Y_USOS_DE_LA_RED_DE_CANALES_DE_CH.
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Rick, J. (2021). NUEVOS CONCEPTOS SOBRE LA SECUENCIA CONSTRUCTIVA Y USOS DE LA RED DE CANALES DE CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR (*) NEW CONCEPTS ON THE CONSTRUCTIVE SEQUENCE AND FUNCTIONS OF THE CANALS' NETWORK OF CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR. Devenir, 8(15), 75-94.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- URL de la Fuente 1: https://www.academia.edu/107929645/The_Chronology_of_Chav%C3%ADn_de_Hu%C3%A1ntar_and_its_Implications_for_the_Formative_Period
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Rick, J. (2012). The Chronology of Chavin de Huántar and its Implications for the Formative Period, Boletín de Arqueología PUCP, 13, 87-132.
- URL de la Fuente 2: https://www.academia.edu/34206448/Rick_and_Bazan_2017_Reporte_de_la_campa%C3%B1a_de_excavaciones_arqueol%C3%B3gicas_2014_en_Ch
- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Rick & Bazan 2017_Reporte de la campaña de excavaciones arqueológicas 2014 en Chavin de Huántar. Develando y entendiendo nuevos espacios rituales en la explanada norte del edificio C
- URL de la Fuente 3: https://www.academia.edu/107929650/On_the_Acoustics_of_the_Underground_Galleries_of_Ancient_Chav%C3%ADn_de_Hu%C3%A1ntar_Peru
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Rick, J. (2008). On the Acoustics of the Underground Galleries of Ancient Chavin de Huántar, Peru, Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 7214-7218.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Sí

Notes: There are regional and local cults. In the early periods there were no hegemonic cults, but rather diverse religious expressions that converged and maintained a relationship with the recurring representations of certain animals (caiman, snake, condor), plants, etc.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Sí

Notes: Likely yes. Some proposed that there is a certain level of competition between ceremonial centers in the Late Formative period at a regional level, for example with Kuntur Wasi

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Sí

Notes: Competitiveness is determined by different social contacts, it is diverse, it cannot be determined yet

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— Sí

Notes: Could be

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Sí

Notes: Likely yes, but the only indicators of violence that we have for now are indirect from the iconography with severed heads

Reference: Tello, Julio C., Chavín. *Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina*. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Sí

Notes: The Chavín de Huántar site serves as a center of religious initiation, to reach the site there are several routes creating a pilgrimage space. At the level of internal architecture, within the site there are routes that lead to particular spaces such as the galleries, these are more numerous in the ceremonial center, architecturally they are isolated and give the impression of restricting, isolating and limiting income.

Reference: Rick, John W., Silvia R. Kembel, Rosa M. Rick, and John A. Kembel. "La Arquitectura Del Complejo Ceremonial De Chavín De Huántar: Documentación Tridimensional Y Sus Implicancias". *Boletín De Arqueología PUCP*, no. 2 (March 26, 1998): 181-214. <https://doi.org/10.18800/boletindearqueologiapucp.199801.013>.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— El campo lo desconoce

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

— El campo lo desconoce

↳ Assigned by class:

— El campo lo desconoce

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

— El campo lo desconoce

↳ Assigned by gender:

— El campo lo desconoce

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Sí

- ↳ Assigned by some other factor:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:
– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religion have official political support
– Sí

- ↳ Are the priests paid by polity:
 - Sí
 - Notes: The idea that is put forward is that the religious system is almost the same as the political system, almost one.

- ↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Until that moment, the religious system is almost the same as the political system, almost one.

- ↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Likely yes

- ↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:
 - Sí

- ↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
 - Sí
 - Notes: Until that moment, the religious system is almost the same as the political system, almost one.

- ↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
 - El campo lo desconoce

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
– El campo lo desconoce

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- El campo lo desconoce
- Notes: Burger believe that the number of people could be 5,000, but the total cannot be estimated because the homes have not been found in their entirety.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

- El campo lo desconoce

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

- Grupo religioso grande (con grupos religiosos más pequeños que no son permitidos oficialmente pero en la práctica son tolerados)

Notes: There is not enough information to give a clear answer between these options, the most similar is that, being an eclectic cult, there is a certain level of tolerance due to its territorial extension

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Sí

Reference: Ortiz, Miguel, and John Rick. "Accessing the Ancestor Architecture: An Examination of the Galleries of Chavín's Building C Vicinity". In *New Perspectives on the Early Formation of the Andean Civilization Chronology, Interaction, and Social Organization*, 112:19–52. *Senri Ethnological Studies*, 2023. <https://acortar.link/dDhcPF>.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Sí

Notes: It seems to be a hierarchical cult and there must be certain differentiated levels in the religion

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: It is not known if he is a head priest or a group of priests for the region

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Sí

Notes: Attributed to the effects of psychotropic plants

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Powers are inherited:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Sí

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Reference: Tello, Julio C., Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Altura, en metros: 20

Notes: Even though it is not excavated from the base, maximum 20m.

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Altura, en metros: 20

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - El campo lo desconoce

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Sí

Reference: Tello, Julio C., Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

- ↳ Tombs:
 - Sí

Notes: It is difficult to find contexts of tombs/cemeteries during the formative period in the area of extension of the indicated territory.

Reference: Rick, John. "UN ANÁLISIS DE LOS CENTROS CEREMONIALES DEL PERIODO FORMATIVO A PARTIR DE LOS ESTUDIOS EN CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR". Boletín De Arqueología PUCP 10 (2006): 201-14.

- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - Sí

Notes: It is difficult to find contexts of tombs/cemeteries during the formative period in the area of extension of the indicated territory.

Reference: Rick, John. "UN ANÁLISIS DE LOS CENTROS CEREMONIALES DEL PERIODO FORMATIVO A PARTIR DE LOS ESTUDIOS EN CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR". Boletín De Arqueología PUCP 10 (2006): 201-14.

- ↳ Temples:

– Sí

↳ Altars:

– Sí

Notes: Cerro Piruru and the Portada de las Falcónidas

↳ Devotional markers:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Sí

Notes: Chavin de Huantar temple

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Sí

Notes: In the lithic art

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– En algunos espacios públicos

– En todos los espacios públicos

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Sí

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Sí

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Sí

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Sí

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Sí

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Sí

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Sí

Notes: Chavin "trinity" is composed by feline, condor (bird) and snake

↳ Humans:

– Sí

Notes: Cabezas clavos

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Sí

Notes: Plants

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Sí

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Sí

Are pilgrimages present:

– Sí

Notes: Some propose that Chavín is the ceremonial center of pilgrimage, because it is at the center of 3 circles of interaction.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– El campo lo desconoce

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– El campo lo desconoce

Belief in afterlife:

– Sí

Notes: Death in ancient Peru in the Andean worldview is the beginning of life in the culturally extended world of the dead.

Reference: Kaulicke, Peter. MEMORIA Y MUERTE EN EL PERU ANTIGUO. PONTIFICIA UNIVERSIDAD CATOLICA DEL PERU, 2001.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Reincarnation in this world:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: As is known, funerary contexts have not been found at the Chavín de Huántar site, nor have complete burials from the Formative Period.

Reference: Rick, John. "UN ANÁLISIS DE LOS CENTROS CEREMONIALES DEL PERIODO FORMATIVO A PARTIR DE LOS ESTUDIOS EN CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR". Boletín De Arqueología PUCP 10 (2006): 201-14.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

↳ Personal effects:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Valuable items:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other grave goods:
– El campo lo desconoce

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– Sí

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Other formal burial type:
– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Sí

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Sí

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Sí

Notes: The Lanzon represents an anthropomorphic figure with feline features (known as Wira Kocha). The feline is the fundamental basis of all representations of Chavín art.

Reference: Tello, Julio C.. Chavín. Cultura Matriz De La Civilización Andina. Lima, Perú: Fundación Wiese, 2019.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– El campo lo desconoce

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– El campo lo desconoce

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Sí (especifique): The Lanzon has feline representations, snakes, big eyes, fangs, and others.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - El campo lo desconoce
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Sí
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - El campo lo desconoce
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Sí

Notes: The Chavin art has a principal divinity: Wira Kocho and a lot of secondary divinities represented by zoomorphic figures and nature (rain, sun, etc).

 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Sí

- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– El campo lo desconoce

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– El campo lo desconoce

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– El campo lo desconoce

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Una sociedad de jefatura

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– El campo lo desconoce

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Sí

Notes: And to support the Feasts

Reference: Mesía , Christian . "FESTINES Y PODER EN CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR DURANTE EL PERÍODO FORMATIVO TARDÍO EN LOS ANDES CENTRALES". *Chungará* 46 (2014): 313-43.
<https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-73562014000300002> .

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Sí

Notes: The Chavín canals would have formed three main networks that drain towards the Mosna River

Reference: Bustamante, Julio, Enrique Crousillat, and John Rick. "Nuevos Conceptos Sobre La Secuencia Constructiva Y Usos De La Red De Canales De Chavín De Huántar". *Devenir* 8 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.21754/devenir.v8i15.874> .

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– El campo lo desconoce

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– El campo lo desconoce

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— El campo lo desconoce

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— El campo lo desconoce

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Rick (2008) mentions that a probable astronomical alignment has been detected, according to which from near the center of the Circular Plaza one can observe the rising of the Sun over a prominent hill during the summer solstice.

Reference: Rick, John. "Context, Construction, and Ritual in the Development of Authority at Chavín De Huántar". In *Chavín: Art, Architecture and Culture*, edited by Jeffrey Quilter and William Conklin, 3-34, 2008.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— El campo lo desconoce

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— Sí

Notes: Such as Parenchyma, Fabaceae, Poaceae, Zea mays, Chenopodium and others (see table 10:331).

Reference: Mesia, Christian. "FESTINES Y PODER EN CHAVÍN DE HUÁNTAR DURANTE EL PERÍODO FORMATIVO TARDÍO EN LOS ANDES CENTRALES". *Chungará* 46 (2014): 313-43. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-73562014000300002>.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Caza (incluyendo animales marinos)
- Pesca
- Agricultura a pequeña escala/jardines horticolas o huertos

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— El campo lo desconoce

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